

Building an Empire

Sketch by Samuel Danielle, c. 1801. Published 1820.

but the Kgwatlheng were among the original Tswana-speaking people present in Botswana long before the Ngwaketse arrived. They venerate the elephant (tlou) as their totem.

The Ngwaketse entered Botswana c. 1700 and were part of a group known as Kwena, named after their totem kwena (crocodile). The (Ba)Ngwaketse grew in numbers and expanded their territory in much of southern Botswana during the reign of Moleta

A SHORT HISTORY OF THE BANGWAKETSE*

By I. SCHAPERA

I. THE BEGINNINGS OF TRIBAL HISTORY¹

The BaNgwaketse, according to widespread and undisputed tradition, are an offshoot of the BaKwena now living in the BaKwena Reserve of the Bechuanaland Protectorate. The ruling communities of both tribes have the same totem, viz. the crocodile (*kwena*), their Chiefs claim descent from the same ancestors, and the BaNgwaketse acknowledge the BaKwena as their seniors in tribal rank.

There are, however, several conflicting stories about the time and circumstances of the split between the two tribes. It is often said to have taken place when the BaKwena were ruled by Kwena, the elder brother of Ngwato and Ngwaketse (the titular founders of the Ngwato and Ngwaketse tribes respectively). Some state that Ngwaketse and his followers broke away first,

* This is the fourth of a series of articles summarizing the histories of the principal tribes of the Bechuanaland Protectorate. Those already dealt with are the BaTswana (by G. E. Nettleton, in *Bantu Studies*, vol. viii, 1934, pp. 343-60), BagaMaletse (by V. F. Ellenberger, in *Trans. roy. Soc. S. Afr.*, vol. xxv, 1937, pp. 1-72), and BaTlokwa (by V. F. Ellenberger, in *Bantu Studies*, vol. xiii, 1939, pp. 165-98). Shorter versions have also been published in the vernacular by A. J. Wookey, *Dico tsa Seemana* (Third ed., Tlokweng, 1929) and I. Schapera (ed.), *Ditirofalo tsa Merafeyo ya BaTswana* (Lovedale, 1946).

The present article is based mainly upon information obtained during field trips made to the BaNgwaketse in 1938 and 1941. Wherever possible, I have referred to earlier authorities, who are mentioned in the footnotes. In the absence of specific citation, the source of my statements is tribal tradition, as related to me by members of the Chief's *kgotla* at Kanye. The first draft was read by Chief Bathoeng II, to whom I am greatly indebted for several amendments and for help in many other ways. My fieldwork was financed by the E.P. Administration, on whose behalf this article is being published.

¹ Principal Sources: I Schapera, *Ditirofalo tsa Merafeyo ya BaTswana*, chap. V, "BaNgwaketse", pp. 121-33 (information obtained in the Chief's *kgotla* at Kanye, 1938); G. B. Moseley, "History of the BaNgwaketse as supplied by Tiro Motlhabane", MS 1926 (Mafeking Registry, J.67); A. J. Wookey, *Dico tsa Seemana*, pp. 66-68 (information obtained from Chief Bathoeng I).

leaving Ngwato behind with Kwena.² Present-day historians among the Ngwaketse maintain, on the other hand, that the BaNgwato were the first to leave—ostensibly on a hunting expedition, but actually in order to make themselves an independent tribe. Ngwaketse then sought permission to go hunting too. Kwena refused, because of the way in which he had been deserted by the BaNgwato. Ngwaketse nevertheless departed with his followers, and he also did not return.³ This would be about the middle of the seventeenth century, which is the latest date, according to the genealogies of the Chiefs, that can be assigned to Kwena and his brothers.

Tribal traditions go on to say that Ngwaketse and his people, after parting from the BaKwena, settled at Magagarapa (a hill to the south of Mochudi). Thence they went to Kgale (the site of the present Roman Catholic Mission near Gaberones). Here, during the rule of Ngwaketse's son Sečapitsō, they were attacked by the BaKwena, who wished to bring them back to their former allegiance. The BaNgwaketse beat off the attack, and then moved still farther south to Ntuotswane (a hill to the east of the present village of Manyana). Sečapitsō died there, and was succeeded by his son Lešma, in whose reign the tribe moved to Potsane (east of Lekgōlōbōtō). Lešma had two sons, Khuto and Khutwane. Khuto was a weakling and, after Lešma's death, allowed Khutwane to manage the affairs of the tribe on his behalf. The upshot was that Khutwane ultimately usurped the Chieftainship. He took the tribe to Sengōma (a small hill south of the present village of Ramoutsa). After his death, there was a dispute for the Chieftainship between his son Makaba and Khuto's son Modutwa. Makaba fled with his followers to Seōké (Woodlands Farm, Lobatse), where he died and was succeeded by his son Mongala. The Chief-

² Moseley, *op. cit.*; Wookey, *op. cit.*, p. 66.
³ Schapera, *op. cit.*, p. 121.

Unpacking Schapera

An important source for the story of Moleta is a paper published in 1942 by Isaac Schapera titled, 'A short history of the Bangwaketse'. Like many historical texts it isn't easy to read.

Here we unpack and illustrate an excerpt from this text.

Schapera's paper includes a map delineating the Bangwaketse Reserve, which was the product of the colonial administration, and only includes a few of the place-names mentioned in the text.

William J. Burchell, 1822, *Travels in the Interior of South Africa*, London.

Even after Moleta's death, the capital where his son Makaba II resided was known by his father's name ('Melitta' in the map above, published in 1822).

We do not have photographs of any of the people in Moleta’s story, which predates photography. The first photographs we have of BaNgwaketse people come from the generation of **Gaseitsiwe** (?1845-89), three generations following Moleta.

Gaseitsiwe, Ngwaketse kgosi. Photographed by Gustav Theodor Fritsch in 1865, Stellenbosch University Library.

For the story of Moleta, we need to go back further and access other kinds of traces, and use other ways to visualise the past.

"The Ngwaketse chief Gaseitsiwe and his followers in the kgotla, Kanye, Bechuanaland", photographed by Gustav Fritsch in 1865

We can trace Ngwaketse expansion by locating Moleta's many capitals, most of which were built in stone. Some of these

stone walls can still be seen today.

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The Story of Moleta

Extracts from: Schapera, Isaac (1942). A short history of the Bangwaketse, African Studies, 1:1, 1-26, DOI: 10.1080/00020184208706566.

*[p.2] Mongala ruled over the BaNgwaketse
whilst they were living at Seôkê.*

The story of **Moleta** begins when his father **Mongala** was kgosi and settled at Seôkê near present Lobatse. Some of the stonewall remains of Seôkê are still standing and cover a large area.

See Walls

The meaning of the word Seôkê is unclear, but it could come from -oka (se-oke/a) referring to a large animal, such as an elephant. But se-oka also means ‘something that entices or allures’ (Cole and Moncho-Warren, Macmillan Setswana-English Dictionary) and comes close to another name for this place, Ntakwetoga, ‘something that comes into view’.

Stone walls in the tall grass

Activate Windows
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*In the same district they had found another tribe, the BaKgwatlheng, who became their subjects. **Mongala** was the sister's son (**setlogolo**) of **Tau**, head of the BaKgwatlheng. At first the two peoples lived together amicably.*

The (Ba)Kgwatlheng were living in Seôkê before the Ngwaketse arrived. For a time, they lived together peacefully and intermarried, as the tradition tells us, but then conflict arose.

Samuel Daniell, 1804

Man cooking and fanning fire. Sketch by Samuel Daniell, 1820.

As Mongala's uncle on the maternal side, known as his *malome*, Tau held an important role in protecting and supporting his nephew Mongala.

*A dispute then arose owing to some injury inflicted upon Tau's son **Seeisô** by Mongala's son **Moleta**. The BaKgwatheng, failing to receive satisfaction, decided to leave the BaNgwaketse*

Some of the Kgwatheng took refuge among the Rolong, who are made up of a number of groups, among them the Tshidi Rolong in the **Molopo River** region.

It is said that they all stole away from their village one night, leaving behind some cattle and goats in their kraals to allay suspicion for the time being. They trekked through the Phata-ya-Barwa pass (where the main road from Kanye enters Lobatsi), and after crossing the Moselebe River went on towards Segeng.

[See Route from Phata-ya-Barwa to Segeng](#)

*The BaNgwaketse, hearing the animals in the kraals, at first did not realise that the BaKgwatlheng had deserted them ; but the ruse was soon discovered, and Mongala set out with a small commando to bring them back. He found them settled at Kgalong-loo-Tau, near Segeng. He attacked them, but was defeated, and he himself was captured and speared to death. The spot where this happened has ever since been known as **Ga-Tlhaba** (from go tlhaba, to stab).*

Bootchuana Weapons, Plate IV, Campbell, 1815

*Mongala's son **Moleta** then became Chief of the BaNgwaketse (c. 1770?). His first act was to avenge his father's death. He attacked the BaKgwatlheng at **Kgalong-loo-Tau**, and defeated them so decisively that their tribe was destroyed. Some fled south to the BaRolong. Others fled to Ngologa, in the Kalahari Desert* and became the people now known as BaKgalagadi-baNgologa.*

BaKgwatlheng's Flee

The Ngologa are regarded as a group of the original Tswana-speaking people who moved into the dry Kalahari after being pushed west by the incoming Kwena, Ngwaketse and other latecomers.

Some time after this, the BaNgwaketse became involved in a war with the BaTlhaping, Korana, and other southern tribes. Moleta was advised to build protective walls in order to resist the attacks of his enemies.

It is not clear what caused this war, but likely Moleta's people had begun to steal cattle from the Tlhaping, who were established in the Harts River area.

He therefore moved from Seôkê to Pitsa (a hill overlooking Lobatsi), and surrounded his new

village with stone walls.

G.J Wood, 1878

Pitsa in Setswana means a pot, which may refer to Pitsa's location on the slopes of a depression surrounded by hills.

Stone walls at Pitsa

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A battle took place in the pass henceforth named Phata-ya-Barwa (after these southern tribes), and the invaders were defeated and driven off.

Phata ya Barwa, literally ‘pass [to] the South, is the direction south from present Lobatse the modern highway takes to Mahikeng in South Africa. The pass is formed by a dip or stirrup between two hills.

[Go to Pitsa](#)

[Go to Phata Ya Barwa](#)

*Moleta also fought against the BaHurutshe, who were his neighbours to the east. Their Chief at the time was **Boikanyo**. He had been acting as regent for his half-brother **Tirwê**, but subsequently refused to hand over the Chieftainship, Tirwê appealed to the BaNgwaketse, who helped him to defeat and kill Boikanyo at Pôwê (the small hill in front of the Mission Station at Dinokana).*

The BaHurutshe are made up of many groups, in this case the Bahurutshe ba ga Gopane.

Moffat 1842

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*From Pitsa Moleta moved to Makolontwane
(north-east of Moshaneng, in the present Ba-
Ngwaketse Reserve).*

Moshaneng, or Moshana Village, is located 10 kms west of Kanye, the capital of Botswana's southern district. The Bangwaketse Reserve was a colonial area created by the British who ruled over the Bechuanaland Protectorate (1885-1966), known since independence as Botswana.

Stonewalling at Makolontwane, the Ngwaketse capital established c. 1780

The meaning of Makolontwane is unclear. Literally it means 'tadpoles' (baby frogs) and may refer to the two streams that flow on either side of the main compound.

*He took the tribe to Mhakane, near Mabule, on the Mólôpo River. While they were there, his son **Makaba** went on a raiding expedition against the BaKgalagadi-baNgologa at Lehututu, and brought back many cattle, with very long horns, whose progeny are still known as dingologa.*

Longhorned 'Sanga'

During these years of expansion, Moleta was busy forming young men into militia units. These men came not just from the Ngwaketse but from the people Moleta's army defeated.

Date	Place	Mephato	meaning
c. 1772	Seoke	MaSwama	'fan lillies'
c. 1774	Seoke	MaTshwarakgomo	'cattle rustlers'
c. 1776	Pitsa	MaLetlathebe	'bring the shields'
c. 1778	Pitsa	MaNkwe	'leopards'
c. 1780	Makolontwane	MaThibaphata	'defenders of the pass'
c. 1782	Makolontwane	MaTshologa	'invaders'
c. 1784	Setlhabatsane	MaNoga	'snakes'
c. 1786	Setlhabatsane	MaTimakgabo	'monkey extinguishers'
c. 1788	Setlhabatsane	MaGaga	'caves'

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The BaNgwaketse afterwards returned to the north and settled at Setlhabatsane (west of Moshaneng), where Moleta died (c. 1790). The missionary traveller John Campbell was told in 1820, by a MoRolong who had lived for some time among the BaNgwaketse, that Moleta was poisoned by Makaba, who loved one of his father's wives and wanted her for himself.

The BaNgwaketse themselves say that he died of old age. The story is that he was in the kgotla, and got up to go into the adjoining cattle kraal, but his strength gave way, and he fell down dead facing the gate of the kraal

[Cape Province]. W. G. Burchell, Lantern Slides, 1811-1812.

Source: Royal Geographical Society (with IBG)

Moleta's Capitals

Click and explore for more information on the capitals of Moleta

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Makaba II

Moleta was succeeded by his son **Makaba II**, who seems to have been between thirty and forty years old at the time. Makaba was a warrior Chief under whom the BaNgwaketse became the strongest and most feared tribe in all Bechuanaland. At one time or another he fought against almost all the tribes surrounding him, and although he met with several reverses, he was more often victorious.

Sketch by Samuel Daniëlle, c. 1801. Published 1820.

His reign coincided with the arrival of the first European travellers and missionaries in Southern Bechuanaland. Their contemporary accounts of the Ba-Ngwaketse, although usually based solely on hearsay, provide a very useful supplement to local traditions, and enable us to speak with more accuracy and authority about the course of tribal history from now on.

Ngwaketse women and children, Bechuanaland.

(EM-SMB/32/879)

Unfortunately, it is not always possible to determine from them the true chronological sequence of the many campaigns and raids in which Makaba is said to have engaged. All that we can do, therefore, is to arrange in what seems to be the most satisfactory order the more outstanding events of his reign.

Soon after his accession, Makaba began fighting against the BaKwena, with whom he was on hostile terms ever after. He is said to have tricked them, by professions of friendship, into mixing their cattleposts with his; he then fell upon them suddenly, defeated them, and looted many of their cattle.

c.1713 drawing of a sanga cow. Unknown artist. https://www.loc.gov/resource/gdcwdl.wdl_11264/?r=0.058,0.253,0.364,0.232,0.

Campbell (in 1820) was informed that on this occasion Makaba captured the Kwena Chief Seitlhamo, whom, however, he soon afterwards liberated. Later he again attacked the BaKwena, and this time he killed Seitlhamo.

This "so enraged the Boquains," continues Campbell, " that they rallied and made a furious attack upon Makkabba, killed many of his people, and captured a great number of their cattle."

The attack referred to here was probably the one led by Seitlhamo's son Maleke, who, according to Kwena accounts, burned Makaba's ^[p. 4] village at Kanye and killed one of his uncles named Tawana.

Makaba at the time was living at **Sebatleng** (to the west of Kanye Hill), to which he had moved from Setlhabatsane. Following upon his defeat by the BaKwena, he settled at the top of Kanye Hill, which he fortified with stone walls whose remains are still visible. Here he was attacked, about 1798 or 1799, by some BaRolong-booRatlou, Korana, and Griquas, led by a European renegade named Jan Bloem. He beat off the attack so successfully that none of his cattle were looted.

Bloem died very shortly afterwards, supposedly of drinking water from a well poisoned by the BaNgwaketse.

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Kanye Hill

On another occasion, Makaba was challenged by the BaKgatlabagaMmanaana of **Mabotsa** (Maanwane), who resented a visitor's taunt that they were not as brave as the BaNgwaketse.

He fought with them on the Ngotwane River, and defeated them so decisively that they were scattered and all their cattle looted. Kontle, their Chief, then came with his followers to Makaba to beg for cattle. They were accepted into the tribe, and built their village first at Mogopyana (east of Kanye) and then at GaMafikana (nearer Kanye), where the section of BaKgatla under headman Ketlogetswe Malete is living today. Kontle afterwards married one of Makaba's daughters, by whom he begot a son named **Mosielele**.

Booswana Hut by Samuel Daniell, *African Scenery and Animals* of 1804–5

Somewhat later, about 1808, Makaba was joined by various groups of BaRolong who had been driven from home by civil wars. During the next few years he made successful cattle raids upon the BaTlhaping, BaKwena, BaHurutshe and other tribes, who at last combined to attack him. It is said by the BaNgwaketse that the alliance was promoted by Makaba's uncle Moabi, whom he had driven away because of a personal quarrel about one of Moleta's widows.

Makaba then moved to **Pitsaneng** (east of Kanye); thence he went to **Mokakanana**, near Mafeking; and afterwards he returned to Kanye, settling where the Sebako ward (under headman Sebati Dikgageng) is now located. A big olive tree is still standing where he had his kgotla. The dates of these various moves cannot be ascertained, but it was probably about 1815 that Makaba returned to Kanye. Soon afterwards most of the BaRolong staying with him went back to their

own country, although a few small groups remained behind at Moshaneng as part of the Ngwaketse tribe.

By this time, Makaba was the most powerful Chief in Southern Bechuanaland. The BaTlhaping, who had sent several expeditions against him, usually with disastrous results, feared and hated him.

Some time after Campbell's first visit, Makaba was again at war with the BaTlhaping, probably ^[p.5] in 1816 or 1817. One of their commandoes had passed through his territory to attack the Ba-Kwena. They were driven back, and while they were making their way home he ambushed, defeated, and scattered them. He afterwards raided both the BaHurutshe and the BagaMalete, and looted many of their cattle.

Early in 1820, however, he himself lost many cattle to “*a nation beyond him*” probably the BaKwena.

“He had recaptured the cattle,” says Campbell, “but he wished now to execute vengeance on them for the aggression.”

To this end he tried to recruit allies from among the neighbouring tribes, but, meeting with no success, he abandoned the projected raid.

In 1820 Campbell again visited the BaTlhaping. He found them as hostile as ever against Makaba, and when he expressed a desire to visit that Chief they strongly opposed him. He went instead to the BaHurutshe, then living at Kaditshwene, near the modern town of Zeerust. Here he received messages from Makaba inviting him to the BaNgwaketse also, but he refused.

“We considered that his object in sending for us, must either have been to obtain beads, or to take us with him on a predatory expedition. Of the first we had none, to the latter we were indisposed.”

At the time Makaba had staying with him the notorious Dutch renegade **Coenraad Buys**, but, on learning of Campbell's presence in the vicinity, Buys went farther north to the BaNgwato, among whom he died shortly afterwards. He was not the first European to establish direct contact with the BaNgwaketse, for as early as 1807 or 1808 they had been visited by some **Korana Hottentots** and a European missionary (**Rev. W. Edwards**) from Klaarwater, who traded with them for ivory.

Kwena women and children bringing produce to sell, Ntsweng. (EM-SMB/32/872)

Makabba's Capitals

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